

FRENCH IN LITERATURE PARABLE TRADITIONS

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Abstract: The article gives a brief description of the period in which the famous French writer Jean de La Fontaine lived. The research paper also analyzes a number of myths presented by the author depicting human deficiencies.

Key-words: French myth, Aesopian language, allegory, morality

Introduction

Parable (Arab . — sample , example) — didactic literature genre . Educational in character , mostly small poetic , sometimes prose in the form of work In the example to a person special features , to society special social events , relationships birds , animals between relationships and nature events by means of reflection will be delivered . In literature traditional allegorical method there is From this except cryptography , author's his opinion idea on purpose disguise for from allegories use method is also available and called him " deceiver it is also possible to say " tools " . Authors in his works allegory, irony , paraphrase , legendary " characters " , transparent contextual from nicknames using creativity they did Ancient Greek of literature half legendary figure , from AD in the 4th century BC lived of the fabulist Aesop to his autobiography appeal if we do , it one separately historical person to say that it was possible not He is on the island of Samos lived one Remember a slave has been and it is from AD in the earlier periods of 570-526 lived Egypt at the command of king Amasis according to the Delphics by killed said information is also available . His life about never how scientific information no was That's it period Aesopia language said term is the name of Aesop the fabulist with called From there face from more than time after of Pontus Heraclides Aesop from Thrace the arrival of Perekids contemporary that it was and his the first the boss Xanthus the fact that it is said , but that's it information that's it Herodotus from the story unsure conclusions using take comes out Later on Aristophanes " Already Aesop's death him blame for reason has been thrown away bowl lost motive and from his death before said eagle and beetle about about the fairy tale in detail information gives V century At the end of lived a comedian Plato Aesop's from his death next reincarnation remind past Aesop comedy wrote a comedian Alexis his own with hero Solon collides with , that is , it already is Aesop legend seven wise man and the king Croesus about legends in the form of knit released His contemporary This is Lysippos version knows it was seven of the sage At the beginning of Aesop describes . of Xanthus slavery , seven wise man with communication , Delphic of the priests from his trickery death such as all motifs of the IV century to the end come developed gone Then they are Aesopia of the legend joints became From AD previous Antique period in literature Aesop's historicity doubt not done , and Aesop's legendary own of the era to hypercriticism special has been solution doer feature with those who noted , of the V century to the end Come , Aristophanes during in Athens Aesop's of fairy tales written collection

known said that it was data available to him according to children at school trained ; " You ignorant and lazy without a person , even "You haven't even studied Aesop ," he says Aristophanes one the hero From this it seems Aesop's in his works heroes goodness and to the good starter , to others example to be images through described These are never how artistic without exaggeration , without finishing , prosaic repetitions was Indeed , Aesop the so -called collection direction different of periods legends own into takes French poet , writer , famous scientist , French of the academy member (since 1684) - Jean-de-La Fontaine - July 8, 1621 in Chateau - Thierry , Champagne born .of La Fontaine parable genre works more fame won " Poetic fairy tale and in the collections " stories " (books 1-5, 1665-85), " Proverbs " (books 1-12, 1668-94) sharp funny , big thinker , in literature Wake up period traditions successor as to the field came out His antique period , Europe and East literature (" Kalila and Dimna " and others), as well as the people from his wisdom encouraged created parables modernity , sharp comic , descriptions brightness with the world satirical literature treasure enriched . Uzbek and Russian parable in the development of La Fontaine's work important there is a place . " Kosib and The parable of the shopkeeper was translated into Uzbek in 1984 to the language translation done.

He is his fairy tale creativity Aesop's translations with started and new of time famous to the fabulist became (XVII century). La of Fontaine creative rich heritage : poems , poems , fairy tales and stories in poetry , in prose), but the world in his literature it is mainly legend genre developed and becoming a rich fabulist left.

La Fontaine works to the composition main part , entry and concepts enters Each of the parables different different poetic to forms have Poetic in the 17th century form everyone by acceptance not done , therefore for they are free in style written The author and his contemporaries to his opinion according to , free poem editor sign for more suitable was The fabulist Jean de La Fontaine is the author of , from time to time with , only inspiration with creativity they believe that they did . Nevertheless , his creative legacy different in genres created works own into takes They are between mythological poems and comedies there is From this except , Lafontaine descriptive of the genre to the founder became His in his work lyrical there are also operas . However , it is the world to literature very humble the title is 'La Fontaine's bytes with moved Aesop's the name " tales " . with come in came His creativity french of literature high is an achievement . And of La Fontaine artistic discoveries another countries in literature legend genre development in advance set gave

La Fontaine the most famous legends :

- Wolf and a dog
- Wolf and Heron
- Wolf and lamb
- Wolf , goat and a child
- Wolf the shepherd
- Crow and fox
- Thieves and donkeys
- Pigeon and ant
- Two a goat

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